
135. Triple star systems

STELLAR MULTIPLICITY is a ubiquitous outcome of star formation. The frequency and properties of multiple star systems, and their dependence on mass and environment, provide powerful probes of the star-formation process. Gaia's deep and uniform binary survey is already providing some important clues in the ability to distinguish between their formation, either by turbulent core fragmentation or gravitationally unstable disk accretion (El-Badry et al., 2019).

Binaries provide many other astrophysical insights: their masses underpin estimates of stellar structure, age, and composition; their orbits reveal the presence of rare unseen objects such as black holes and neutron stars; and the interaction between close components can significantly influence their evolution, giving rise to a great variety of structural and dynamical phenomena.

WHAT FRACTION of stars in our Galaxy are binary? Estimates range from as little as 30–35% (e.g. Lada, 2006), to perhaps 80%, although the question must be phrased more precisely for it to have a meaningful answer: the binary fraction differs for visual, astrometric, and spectroscopic binaries, for wide-separation binaries, and with a dependency, again as shown by recent Gaia results, on metallicity (El-Badry & Rix, 2019).

A RELATED question is the occurrence of higher multiplicity systems, viz. triple, quadruple, and higher order. Among field objects, the multiplicity and width of the orbital period distribution are steep functions of the primary mass, i.e. the likelihood of being in a binary or multiple system increases as the component masses increase (Duchêne & Kraus, 2013).

Most higher-order systems are therefore triple, with four or more components being less common (Tokovinin, 1997; 2001). In the 1999 revision of his catalogue of multiple stars, for example, 551 of the 728 higher multiplicity systems are triple (Tokovinin, 2004), although these sorts of conclusions were often subject to strong selection effects in the days before much larger and more uniform surveys became available.

Despite their importance in further constraining theories of star formation, even a relatively complete census of triple systems has proved challenging. Raghavan et al. (2010) defined a sample for solar-type stars within 25 pc, with a total number of only 56 systems. Extension of this effort to smaller masses (Winters et al., 2019), or to larger distances (Tokovinin, 2014a), has been hampered by the lack of a uniform coverage of the parameter space in the full range of periods and mass ratios.

A fairly complete Hipparcos sample of F and G dwarfs within 67 pc contained 4847 primary stars, with 2196 known stellar pairs; some of them belonging to 361 systems ranging from triples to quintuples (Tokovinin, 2014a). In his subsequent analysis, Tokovinin (2014b) found a multiplicity rate ($n \geq 2$) of 46%, a log-normal period distribution with median of 100 yr, and a nearly uniform mass-ratio distribution, independent of period. The fraction with ≥ 3 components was 0.13 ± 0.01 , and the fractions with $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ components were 54:33:8:4:1.

WHAT DOES Gaia, and its unprecedented astrometric and photometric census, have to say about the occurrence of *triple* star systems?

Amongst the most detailed studies of multiple stars to date (much more exacting samples will follow with future data releases!), the EDR3 million-star *binary* compilation of El-Badry et al. (2021, §2.1) actively *removed* triple systems from their binary star catalogue, so this gives us no clues. The reason for doing so is because it becomes far more complex, and requires more extensive astrometric data, to identify triple systems with any degree of statistical certainty, and even more so for quadruple or higher multiplicity systems.

A specific effort to identify triple systems *resolved* by Gaia was made by Tokovinin (2022), who started with the Gaia Catalogue of Nearby Stars, within 100 pc, and based on common proper motions and other criteria, identified 392 hierarchical triple systems (i.e., those in 'nested' orbits, and with limited mutual interaction), along with 30 quadruples and one quintuple, ξ Sco.

GIVEN ITS selection uniformity, and its size, this sample is unprecedented in its unbiased census of wide triples. Among a number of interesting insights, Tokovinin (2022) concluded that: (a) the median primary mass is $0.71M_{\odot}$, and all components of these triples are more massive than the average field star; (b) the median inner and outer separations are 151 and 2570 au respectively, with their median ratio of 14.7 suggesting that many wide triples are just above the dynamical stability limit; (c) the inner and outer orbits are aligned almost randomly, with an average mutual inclination of $83^{\circ} \pm 5^{\circ}$; (d) mean eccentricities, inferred from models, suggest a mean inner value, 0.66 ± 0.02 , resembling a thermal distribution, but a smaller mean outer value, 0.54 ± 0.02 , resulting from dynamical instabilities which remove more eccentric outer orbits.

This sample of *wide* triples, it should be emphasised, represents only a small fraction of *all* such hierarchical systems, whose inner pairs are mostly unresolved by Gaia. While their periods and mass ratios are unknown, their existence can be inferred from the increased astrometric noise, or variable radial velocities. Tokovinin (2022) estimated that the total number of triple systems within 100 pc may be around 10 000.

Tokovinin (2023) produced such a list of 8000 candidate multiples derived from wide binaries found in the Gaia Catalogue of Nearby Stars, selected as those where one (or both) components have excessive astrometric noise (or with other indicators of inner subsystems).

A subset of 1243 southern candidates were observed with high angular resolution at the 4.1-m SOAR telescope, and 503 new pairs with separations 0.03–1 arcsec were resolved, allowing estimates of the inner mass ratios and periods. Another 621 hierarchies with known inner periods are present in the Gaia non-single star catalogue of astrometric and spectroscopic orbits (Arenou et al., 2022). These two non-overlapping groups, combined with existing ground-based data, bring the total number of known nearby hierarchies to 2754.

LET ME RECALL that one of the objectives in characterising the considerable complexity of binary and higher multiplicity stellar systems is in order to understand the underlying processes of star formation, for example whether the result of core fragmentation or gravitationally unstable disk accretion, and the subsequent structural and dynamical evolution of multiple systems.

ONE ASPECT of this is the long-debated mechanism underlying the formation of very close binaries, for which many orbits are inferred to have decreased by a factor 10–100 since formation. Specifically, many main-sequence stars have companions at a few stellar radii, far closer than predicted by star-formation models. These compact binaries are often accompanied by a more distant tertiary, but with characteristics of the inner and outer binaries notably distinct from the general binary population (e.g. Fabrycky & Tremaine, 2007). This has led to suggestions that their formation may be associated with the Kozai–Lidov resonance mechanism.

This somewhat non-intuitive effect in hierarchical triples was discovered by Kozai (1962) for asteroid orbits, and independently by Lidov (1962) for artificial and natural satellite orbits. If the inner binary orbit is initially circular, there is a critical inclination between inner and outer binaries such that the orbit of the inner binary does not remain circular as it precesses: both the eccentricity of the inner binary and the mutual inclination execute periodic oscillations.

Such a mechanism is also believed to operate in the case of some exoplanet orbits, which may (partially) explain the existence of very large eccentricities, and the existence of hot Jupiters (e.g. Perryman, 2018, §10.10.6).

Hwang (2023) used Gaia DR3 to search for resolved tertiary companions (with separations of $10^3 - 10^4$ au) to close (eclipsing, spectroscopic, and astrometric) binary systems. He found that the wide tertiary fraction increases with decreasing orbital period of the inner binary. With the inferred eccentricities of wide tertiaries consistent with a thermal distribution, and similar to those of wide binaries at similar separations, his results appear to exclude the Kozai–Lidov mechanism as an explanation for most wide tertiaries, at least at $> 10^3$ au.

I WILL FINISH with just two examples of systems whose properties are being advanced by the Gaia data.

Gaia DR2 astrometry, in combination with SDSS photometry, has led to the discovery of the first resolved triple white dwarf, J1953–1019 (Perpinyà-Vallès et al., 2019). All three members have pure-hydrogen (DA) atmospheres, masses $0.60 - 0.63M_{\odot}$, and cooling ages of 40–290 Myr, consistent with coeval evolution.

The nearest known *quintuple* systems are GJ 644 at 6.4 pc and ζ UMa at 8.3 pc. Tokovinin (2020) derived the properties of κ Tuc and ζ Sco, at 21 and 28 pc respectively, both composed of solar-type stars. Strongly correlated masses and wide orbits can be explained if those systems formed by fragmentation in relative isolation and their components accreted gas from a common source, as expected in a hierarchical collapse.

FUTURE GAIA releases will enrich the 100-pc triple star sample by adding close resolved binaries, and providing astrometric and spectroscopic orbits for many.